

MATILDE

Migration Impact Assessment to Enhance
Integration and Local Development in
European Rural and Mountain Regions

FIRST POLICY REPORT

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- H2020-EU.3.6.1.2. Trusted organisations, practices, services and policies that are necessary to build resilient, inclusive, participatory, open and creative societies in Europe, in particular taking into account migration, integration and demographic change

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Migration Impact Assessment to Enhance Integration and Local Development In European Rural And Mountain Areas – MATILDE

1. Introduction

Rural areas are often associated with out-migration, population shrinkage, economic weakness and the associated poor provision of services and infrastructure (e.g., Schipfer, 2005). This description also reflects the picture of "places left behind", drawn by Rodríguez-Pose (2018). On the one hand, there are prosperous agglomerations that attract companies and workers and where potential employees and companies benefit from a wide range of reciprocal choices. On the other hand, there are rural regions struggling with the challenges linked to demographic change, the departure of the younger generation and its negative consequences for the economic and innovation potential of the region. A negative development spiral can arise (Weber & Fischer, 2010). The loss of population and the resulting lower demand results in a loss of know-how, innovation potential, and a decline in private and public supply infrastructure, which results in a declining attractiveness of the region and further out-migration. However, there is also an opposite development noticeable, where international migration processes result in "New Immigration Destinations" (McAreevey 2017), and growing, prosperous rural areas (Krajewski & Wiegandt, 2020).

MATILDE is based on the assumption that foreign immigration can be an opportunity for rural and mountainous regions, which are often considered as "left behind". However, social and economic impact of international (third-country) migration needs to be evaluated, accompanied by inclusion measures and acknowledged accordingly. **Hence, MATILDE addresses two problems in parallel: the successful development of rural areas through the successful social and economic inclusion of Third Country Nationals (TCNs).**

Several fields of public policy and related questions are addressed in this context: labour market policy (e.g., access to the labour market), educational policy (e.g., education as enabler for social mobility), social policy (e.g., strengthening social cohesion), integration policy as a

cross-cutting policy (e.g., combating discrimination and racism), economic and innovation policy (e.g., strengthening the economic performance in rural regions), infrastructure policy (e.g., improving the quality of and access to services for all those living in these areas), location and regional policy as well as spatial planning (e.g., the balance and transfer between urban and rural areas).

2. Evidence and Analysis

The MATILDE - First Policy Report provides an insight into selected challenges and most policy-relevant findings that can be identified for several MATILDE rural regions. The insights presented are based on an analysis of the empirical and evidence-based results of WP3 (social impact assessment) and WP4 (economic impact assessment). As WP5 (case studies in the 13 rural MATILDE regions) is still in the process of implementation, it does not yet present in-depth findings on that, but provides initial insights.

DEMOGRAPHIC AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN MATILDE RURAL AREAS

The findings show that the MATILDE regions are quite different with regard to their type of area: Some of them (e.g., Turin/IT and Bursa/TR) are “predominantly urban”, others are “predominantly rural” (e.g., Gudbrandsdalen/NO, Dalarna/SE, North Karelia/FI or Bolzano/IT), some are “intermediate” regions (East Ayrshire and North Ayrshire mainland/UK, Huesca/ES or Haskovo/BG); many of them are also border regions (e.g., Huesca/ES, Bolzano/IT, Turin/IT, Carinthia, Villach/Austria, or Gudbrandsdalen/NO, Ostrobothnia/FI, North Karelia, FI, Dalarna/SE or Haskovo/BG) and some of them are non-mountain regions (e.g., Dalarna/SE, North Karelia/FI, East Ayrshire and North Ayrshire mainland/UK, Ostrobothnia/FI, Haskovo/BG).

Many of the MATILDE regions are particularly affected by negative demographic developments and often stand out from the rest of the country’s development, for example for Carinthia/AT, the sharpest population decline out of all Austrian provinces is predicted by 2040, although nationwide growth is projected, and in Norway, the working-age population is expected to increase, while the working-age population of the MATILDE-region Innlandet is predicted to decrease by -2.69%. However, there are also exceptions, as the region of Bolzano/IT shows. While all Italian NUTS 2-regions would have suffered from a downturn in working-age population, Bolzano’s working-age population is the only one in Italy predicted to grow by 2.73% till 2040. Concerning the demographic and economic development, the

MATILDE economic analyses reveal that the rural areas are generally more disadvantaged with regard to education level, unemployment, population development and the connected development of working-age population compared to urban areas.

MIGRANTS (TCNS) CONTRIBUTE POSITIVELY TO LOCAL ECONOMIES AND TERRITORIES' REVITALIZATION

The analyses show that migrants (TCNs; they are mentioned extra as there is a special focus on this group) contribute positively to local economies by mitigating labour shortages (e.g., in tourism, care or agriculture), triggering innovations, enlarging local markets' offers and creating new services which also means additional jobs. In addition, their presence increases the internationality and diversity of companies' workforces and promotes the companies' internationalization processes, which often leads to the development of new markets due to the additional cultural know-how and their multilingualism. Moreover, the MATILDE social and economic impact analyses reinforce what have been discussed in initial international studies, namely the potential of revitalization that international/TCN migration (including refugee migration) brings to rural areas, i.a. mitigating population loss, maintaining local supply and important services (e.g., care) by migrant entrepreneurship and contributing to local and regional labour supply, and maintaining infrastructure (e.g., schools, grocery shops).

... BUT THEY FACE SEVERAL SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC INCLUSION BARRIERS

The results of the social and economic impact analyses show the clear need for and potential of migrants (TCNs), and at the same time the many challenges they face. The following examples present a selection of particularly urgent difficulties, based on the first findings.

- While some MATILDE countries and regions dependent on immigration (e.g., in terms of labour shortages and population shrinking), and migrants are contributing to sustain local economies, the empirical results confirm that migrant workers often have to take up **jobs that are poorly paid, precarious and not accepted by the local population**. Furthermore, they often experience **exploitation**, i.a. poor legal work conditions, informal work, long working hours, informal housing in the workplace. However, poor working conditions have been exacerbated by the negative consequences of **COVID-19 and the Brexit** in the UK. As both restrict mobility and interrupts migration chains, new migrant workers cannot be recruited easily and existing migrant employees often

have to work longer hours, which often causes discontentment among the employees and can lead them to quit their job, as the case study findings in the Western Isles show. In general, migrant workers are often forced to **stick in passive roles and lack opportunities for personal and professional growth, agency and empowerment.**

- The labour market entry of migrants is often hampered by the **not-adequate and slow recognition of qualifications and university degrees** (e.g., for doctors and nurses), the **lack of or limited language skills** of local and regional labour markets, and **discrimination and racism** expressed by employers, which particularly affects Muslim women with headscarves which disadvantages them from accessing the labour market.
- Often a **mismatch of migrants' skills and their work places** (they are often employed below their qualifications) can be observed, as well as a mismatch between vocational skills and industry needs. This disables immigrants to find better jobs in the formal economy, on the one hand. On the other hand, **regions waste productivity and innovation** as the migrants (TCNs) are often employed in low-productive, but labour-intensive branches.
- Migrants (TCNs) often face problems in presenting the required formalized **competencies to start a business** and to become an entrepreneur. This leads to frustration, especially as gaining these competences is expensive and time-intensive.
- However, not only migrants face problems; employers also face hurdles in employing migrants (TCNs), for example, if certain professions are urgently needed on the local labour market (e.g., fishing industry in the Western Isles/UK), but are not put on the **Shortage Occupation List**. Particular challenges for employers have been caused by **COVID-19** and the **Brexit**, especially for employers in UK's rural case study areas. Both have hampered mobility which resulted in difficulties in recruiting workers (e.g., in the UK case study areas in particular from European countries like Latvia, Romania and Poland which had provided labour force in the last 20 years). The impossibility to recruit migrant workers **threatens local economic sectors** (e.g., fishing industry in Western Isles or agriculture in Spain and Italy, because harvest workers are missing).
- The MATILDE analyses reveal that the potential of migrants (TCNs) only can be fruitful if the framework conditions fit. This includes considering the **barriers to social integration. A lack of (affordable) housing supply**, often combined with complicated access to rent apartments or to buy property, hampers the social inclusion process of

migrants (TCNs). However, housing is also very important for asylum seekers, as **smaller and regional shelters and care facilities** can contribute to build positive networks to locals and the region. This in turn can **increase the willingness of refugees to remain in the rural region** after being granted asylum, which contribute to stabilize the population and economic development in these rural areas.

- **Racism and discrimination** show up in most of the MATILDE regions and that is not only a barrier for labour market entry, but for example also for getting access to housing and it is **hampering the active social participation** of migrants (TCNs) in everyday life in the MATILDE regions. Especially refugees and migrants with visible migrant background are confronted with negative perceptions by locals.
- A **lack of services of general interest in rural areas** (e.g., public transport, schools, health centers, grocery shops, cultural and social offerings) does not only have a negative impact on the migrants' attitude to stay in the region, but also on that of the locals, and makes it even more difficult for all to participate in social life.

3. Policy Implications and Recommendations

Building on the first MATILDE results, the most relevant policy implications and recommendations are:

- The range of available **offers for language learning** varies in the MATILDE regions (e.g., in terms of the language levels available). However, the results show that language acquisition remains an important issue for economic and social inclusion and the offer and access for migrants and asylum seekers should be expanded. However, learning the local language alone is not enough, as results not only from Austria and Italy indicate. It also needs **offers, where migrants (TCNs) can learn about regional and cultural specificities**, as they often lack knowledge about the rural/mountainous region they live in, but also get informed about offers for active participation in rural societies (e.g., participation in clubs). In that context, a particular focus should be put on the **empowerment and active inclusion of migrant women** in social and economic life.
- As the empirical results from the different MATILDE regions reveal, racism and discrimination are major challenges for the economic and social participation of immigrants (TCNs). As not only results for the German case studies show, the attitude of rural inhabitants, employers and co-workers towards TCNs, range from welcoming

and supportive, to apathetic to xenophobia and racism. The attitude of locals is very much influenced by the attitude of local key actors, such as mayors, teachers or entrepreneurs and business people. **Intercultural mediators** can also play an important role to overcome reservations and prejudices and foster the “bridges” between locals and rural newcomers. Hence, initiatives are needed that **promote good interactions between migrants (TCNs) and locals**. This includes to **enable encounters** and offer places of (and time for) interaction as well as bridge building. During the WP5 action research activities, several events and initiatives were created that promote encounter and exchanges. One example is the “intercultural garden” that was created together with local stakeholders in the Bulgarian case study region (Harmanli), where local pupils together with refugee children started planting together flowers and trees. Another example was created within the mountain village of Bussoleno (Turin metropolitan area), where a 4-days architecture workshop has been realized, involving TCNs, local population and students, for the self-building of a convivial wooden structure (“MATILDE big bench”). Such initiatives are needed even more and should be further expanded in rural regions as good-practices offer the chance to learn from each other. However, **openness towards migrants (TCNs)** can also be increased, if local and regional (policy) actors **be aware of and acknowledge the migrants’ (TCNs’) positive social and economic contributions** to local and regional communities and economies.

- As the MATILDE results have shown, there are major barriers for migrants (TCNs) in accessing the labour market as i.a. results from Austria, Norway and Spain indicate. **Structured and fast recognition procedures** are needed where migrants (TCNs) can have their formally acquired qualifications, but also informal and practical qualifications, recognized and certified. There are already examples of this in some countries, but there needs to be a better provision of **information about the recognition process and the benefits of recognition procedures**. In addition, the **needs of regional and local labour markets should be taken more into account** and **migrants should be specifically trained towards labour market needs**. This requires coordinated education and training concepts, including secondary and tertiary education paths. Promoting labour market inclusion of migrants (TCNs), also fosters their social inclusion and help them to better integrate and settle in the region. Considering the local and regional labour market needs (also for e.g., skilled manual

workers), emphasizes the necessity **to review the Shortage Occupation Lists** (which is not only important for UK's rural regions after Brexit), and to pay attention to local and regional labour markets development.

- For different MATILDE regions, such as in Bulgaria or Turkey, measures are requested that **improve refugee integration**. This includes their information about their rights and giving them access to housing, social assistance or health care. Especially in rural areas, where distances to reach the next service center can be large, mobile consultants and, for example, health mediators can offer mobile services.
- Considering the demographic trends presented in this report, which apply to most of the MATILDE regions, measures **that promote the migrants' (TCNs) staying and long-term settlement in the region** are particularly important. Staying in the region can be promoted through labour market integration, which in turn promotes social integration, as outlined before. Hence, measures to enhance the local and regional impacts of migrants (TCNs) need to focus on both, the inclusion at the work-place and in the local communities. As the MATILDE results presented show, local actors, in particular **local policy makers and employers have a key role in the inclusion processes** of migrants (TCNs). It is important that the **whole life cycle of migrants** is considered, in the sense of economic inclusion, that is from the recruiting to on-boarding and the retention phase, as results for Germany show. However, a focus on **family migration and integration processes** are also needed, as this fosters the social integration and the motivation for staying in the region. However, the long-term settlement of migrants (TCNs), which is an important aim for many MATILDE regions, has to be supported by the local communities with **adequate housing policy that secures the sufficient supply and accessibility of housing facilities for all, locals and migrants (TCNs)**. As the explanations show, labour market integration is important for the motivation to stay in the region, but it is not the sole condition. Also important is the aspect of social integration in the region and a sense of well-being. For social integration, in turn, **opportunities for participation and co-creation** are essential. The access to and inclusion in **volunteering activities** (e.g., in clubs or non-profit organizations) can be seen as a key to get access to local societies on the one hand, and it contributes to the local community wellbeing as well as the revitalization of rural areas on the other hand. However, migrants should also be given the opportunity to organise themselves and **establish migrant-led organizations**. Those can cooperate

with other local associations and they often also offer language courses or information events on selected topics for other migrants. As the examples show, these initiatives need the support from local key actors and policy makers. However, there is also a need for **coordinated goals and concepts between the different government levels**, as is emphasized not only for Sweden. Therefore, **strengthening local and regional governance** with placed-based policies considering local population development, labour market and social inclusion needs is vital as the local level is the one where immigration takes place and long-term residence needs to be fostered.

4. Project Identity

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PROJECT WEBSITE

URL: <https://matilde-migration.eu/>

SOCIAL MEDIA

Facebook: <https://www.facebook.com/MatildeProject>
Twitter: https://twitter.com/MATILDE_Mig
LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/matilde-migration/>

Instagram: <https://www.instagram.com/matildemigration/>

Academia: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/matilde-migration/>

ResearchGate: <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Matilde-Migration>

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Further Reading

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